

Proposals for the revision of Viruses, Bacteria and Protista

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Comment from the UDC Editorial Team (UDC Consortium)

A report on the revision of these classes with more details about issues is available in the Comments and Communication section of this volume. Due to the impact the revision of Viruses and Bacteria have on class 6 (especially Medicine), the UDC Editorial Team invites further comments and suggestions for the improvements of the proposed schedules. Classification of Protista has been widely disputed in the literature and equally more input on the proposal would be welcome.

Proposal

- ! 578.8 **Classification of viruses**
SN: *For systematics of viruses, see 578.9*
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is narrowed: the previous description was "Classification and systematics of viruses"]
- ! 578.81 **Viruses primarily of bacterial and Archaean hosts**
Including: Caudovirales and Ligamenvirales
- x 578.811 *(Myoviridae) → 578.911.1*
x 578.812 *(Styloviridae) → 578.911.4*
x 578.813 *(Corticoviridae) → 578.914.8*
x 578.814 *(Microviridae) → 578.921.2*
x 578.815 *(Iroviridae) → 578.914.5*
x 578.816 *(Leviviridae. Masculoviruses) → 578.945.2*
x 578.819 *(Other viruses of this type) → 578.911.2; 578.931.2*
x 578.82/83 *(Viruses primarily of vertebrate hosts) → 578.82; 578.83*
- + 578.82 **Viruses primarily of vertebrate hosts**
Including: Nidovirales
- x 578.821 *(Poxviridae) → 578.914.4*
x 578.822 *(Parvoviridae) → 578.921.1*
x 578.822.9 *(Adeno-associated virus group (AAV)) → 578.921.1*
x 578.823 *(Reoviridae) → 578.931.1*
x 578.824 *(Rhabdoviridae) → 578.951.4*
x 578.825 *(Herpetoviridae) → 578.912.2*
x 578.826 *(Adenoviridae) → 578.914.1*
x 578.827 *(Pavovaviridae) → 578.914.2; 578.914.3*
x 578.828 *(Retroviridae. Retroviruses) → 578.961.1*
- + 578.83 **Viruses primarily of plant, invertebrates and vertebrate hosts**
Including: Picornavirales
- x 578.831 *(Paramyxoviridae) → 578.951.3*

- x 578.832 (*Orthomyxoviridae*) → 578.952.3
- x 578.833 (*Togaviridae*) → 578.944.4
- x 578.833.1 (*Alfavirus*) → 578.944.4
- x 578.833.2 (*Flavivirus*) → 578.944.2
- x 578.833.3 (*Pestivirus*) → 578.944.2
- x 578.833.4 (*Rubivirus*) → 578.944.4
- x 578.834 (*Coronaviridae. Coronaviruses*) → 578.941.1
- x 578.835 (*Picornaviridae. Picornaviruses*) → 578.942.1
- x 578.835.1 (*Enterovirus*) → 578.942.1
- x 578.835.2 (*Rhinovirus*) → 578.942.1
- x 578.835.3 (*Calicivirus*) → 578.944.1
- 578.84 Viruses primarily of invertebrate hosts
- x 578.841 (*Baculoviridae*) → 578.914.6
- x 578.842 (*Iridoviridae*) → 578.914.5
- x 578.85/86 (*Viruses primarily of plant hosts*) → 578.85; 578.86
- + 578.85 Viruses primarily of plants hosts
Including: Tymovirales
- x 578.851 (*Bromovirus*) → 578.944.8
- x 578.852 (*Carlavirus*) → 578.943.3
- x 578.853 (*Caulimovirus*) → 578.971.1
- x 578.854 (*Closterovirus*) → 578.945.1
- x 578.855 (*Comovirus*) → 578.942.2
- x 578.856 (*Cucomovirus*) → 578.944.8
- x 578.857 (*Hordeivirus*) → 578.944.6
- x 578.858 (*Ilarvirus*) → 578.944.8
- + 578.86 Viruses primarily of plant and vertebrate hosts
Including: Mononegavirales
- x 578.861 (*Luteovirus*) → 578.944.3
- x 578.862 (*Nepovirus*) → 578.942.2
- x 578.863 (*Potexvirus*) → 578.943.2
- x 578.864 (*Potyvirus*) → 578.944.7
- x 578.865 (*Tobamovirus*) → 578.944.6
- x 578.866 (*Tobravirus*) → 578.944.6
- x 578.867 (*Tombusvirus*) → 578.944.5
- x 578.868 (*Tymovirus*) → 578.943.1
- x 578.869 (*Other plant viruses*) → 578.85/86
- x 578.89 (*Unclassified viruses and virus-like particles*) → 578.99
- + 578.9 Systematics of viruses
- + 578.91 Group I (dsDNA viruses)
- + 578.911 Caudovirales
- + 578.911.1 Myoviridae

- Including: Bacteriophages: Enterobacteria phages, Escherichia phages and Pseudomonas phages
- + 578.911.2 Podoviridae
Including: Podovirus (Cellulophaga phages and Clostridium phages)
- + 578.911.3 Siphoviridae
Including: Escherichia phages and Enterobacteria phages
- + 578.911.4 Styloviridae
- + 578.912 Herpesvirales
- + 578.912.1 Alloherpesviridae
Including: Batrachovirus and Salmonivirus (Salmonid herpesvirus 1)
IN: *Viruses infecting fish and amphibians*
- + 578.912.2 Herpesviridae
Including: Cytomegalovirus (Human herpesvirus 5); Roseolovirus (Human herpesvirus 6A); Lymphocryptovirus (Epstein-Barr virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates*
- + 578.912.21 Varicellovirus (genus)
Including: Varicella zoster virus and Pseudorabies virus
- + 578.912.22 Simplexvirus (geus)
Including: Human herpesvirus 1 and 2
- + 578.912.3 Malacoherpesviridae
Including: Ostreavirus and Haliotivirus
IN: *Viruses infecting molluscs*
- + 578.913 Ligamenvirales
IN: *Viruses infecting Archaea*
- + 578.913.1 Lipothrixviridae
Including: Alfa-, Beta-, Gamma- and Deltalipothrixvirus
- + 578.913.2 Rudiviridae
Including: Rudivirus (Sulfolobus islandicus virus 1 and 2)
- + 578.914 Unassigned families
Including: Ampullaviridae, Ascoviridae, Bicaudaviridae, Clavaviridae, Fuselloviridae, Globuloviridae, Guttaviridae, Hytrosaviridae, Marseilleviridae, Mimiviridae, Nudiviridae, Nimaviridae, Pandoraviridae, Phycodnaviridae, Plasmaviridae, Polydnviridae, Sphaerolipoviridae, Tectiviridae and Turriviridae
- + 578.914.1 Adenoviridae
Including: Aviadenovirus (Avian adenoviruses) and Mastadenovirus (Human mastadenovirus C)
IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates*
- + 578.914.2 Papillomaviridae
Including: Alpha- and Betapapillomavirus (Papillomaviruses)
SN: *Class here members of the deprecated family Papovaviridae*

- IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates*
- + 578.914.3 Polyomaviridae
Including: Polyomavirus (BK virus, JC virus and Merkel cell virus)
SN: *Class here members of the deprecated family Papovaviridae*
IN: *Viruses infecting mammals and birds*
- + 578.914.4 Poxviridae
Including: Parapoxvirus (Orf virus, Pseudocowpox virus and Bovine papular stomatitis virus); Yatapoxvirus (Tanapox virus and Yaba monkey tumor virus); Molluscipoxvirus (Molluscum contagiosum virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates and invertebrates*
- + 578.914.41 Orthopoxvirus (genus)
Including: Smallpox/variola virus, Vaccinia virus, Cowpox virus and Monkeypox virus
- + 578.914.5 Iridoviridae
Including: Iridovirus and Ranavirus
IN: *Viruses infecting amphibians, reptiles, fishes and invertebrates*
- + 578.914.6 Baculoviridae
Including: Alpha-, Beta-, Gamma- and Deltabaculovirus
IN: *Viruses infecting invertebrates*
- + 578.914.7 Asfarviridae
Including: Asfarvirus (African swine fever virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting insects and mammals*
- + 578.914.8 Corticoviridae
Including: Corticovirus
IN: *Viruses infecting Bacteria*
- + 578.92 Group II (ssDNA viruses)
- + 578.921 Unassigned families
Including: Anelloviridae, Bacillariodnaviridae, Bidnaviridae, Circoviridae, Inoviridae, Nanoviridae and Spiraviridae
- + 578.921.1 Parvoviridae
Including; Parvoviruses: Erythrovirus (Parvovirus B19); Dependoparvovirus (Adeno-associated virus, AAV); Protoparvovirus (Rodent protoparvovirus 1)
IN: *Viruses infecting invertebrates and vertebrates*
- + 578.921.2 Microviridae
Including: Microvirus and Spiromicrovirus
IN: *Viruses infecting Bacteria*
- + 578.921.3 Geminiviridae
Including: Begomovirus (Bean golden yellow mosaic virus); Curtovirus (Beet curly top virus); Mastrevirus (Maize streak virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants*
- + 578.93 Group III (dsRNA viruses)

- + 578.931 Unassigned families
Including: Amalgaviridae, Birnaviridae, Chrysoviridae, Endornaviridae, Hypoviridae, Megabirnaviridae, Partitiviridae, Picobirnaviridae, Quadriviridae and Totiviridae
- + 578.931.1 Reoviridae
Including: Orbivirus (Bluetongue virus, African horse sickness virus and Epizootic hemorrhagic disease virus); Phytoreovirus (Wound tumor virus); Seadornavirus (Banna virus); Coltivirus (Colorado tick fever virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting fungi, plants, invertebrates and vertebrates*
- + 578.931.11 Rotavirus (genus)
Including: Rotaviruses
- + 578.931.2 Cystoviridae
Including: Cystovirus (Pseudomonas phage)
IN: *Viruses infecting Bacteria*
- + 578.94 Group IV ((+)ssRNA viruses)
- + 578.941 Nidovirales
Including: Arteriviridae, Mesoniviridae and Roniviridae
- + 578.941.1 Coronaviridae
Including: Coronaviruses: Betacoronavirus (SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV)
IN: *Viruses infecting mammals and birds*
- + 578.942 Picornavirales
Including: Dicistroviridae, Iflaviridae and Marnaviridae
- + 578.942.1 Picornaviridae
Including: Senecavirus (Senecaviruses)
IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates*
- + 578.942.11 Aphthovirus (genus)
Including: Foot-and-mouth disease virus
- + 578.942.12 Enterovirus (genus)
Including: Enteroviruses, Poliovirus and Rhinovirus
- + 578.942.13 Hepatovirus (genus)
Including: Hepatovirus A
- + 578.942.2 Secoviridae
Including: Cheravirus (Cherry rasp leaf virus); Fabavirus (Broad bean wilt virus 1); Nepovirus (Tobacco ringspot virus); Comovirus (Cowpea mosaic virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants*
- + 578.943 Tymovirales
Including: Gammaflexiviridae
- + 578.943.1 Tymoviridae
Including: Tymovirus (Turnip yellow mosaic virus) and Maculavirus (Grapevine fleck virus)
- + 578.943.2 Alphaflexiviridae

- Including: Potexvirus (Potato virus X)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants and fungi*
- + 578.943.3 Betaflexiviridae
Including: Carlavirus (Carnation latent virus) and Vitivirus (Grapevine virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants and fungi*
- + 578.944 Unassigned families (I)
Including: Alphetetraviridae, Alvernaviridae, Barnaviridae, Benyviridae, Carmotetraviridae, Fusariviridae, Narnaviridae and Permutotetraviridae
- + 578.944.1 Caliciviridae
Including: Lagovirus (Rabbit hemorrhagic disease virus) and Norovirus (Winter vomiting virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates*
- + 578.944.2 Flaviviridae
Including: Hepacivirus (Hepatitis C virus); Pegivirus (Pegiviruses); Pestivirus (Bovine viral diarrhea virus 1)
IN: *Viruses infecting mammals*
- + 578.944.21 Flavivirus (genus)
Including: Yellow fever virus, West Nile virus, Zika virus, Dengue virus and Tick-borne encephalitis virus
- + 578.944.3 Luteoviridae
Including: Polerovirus (Potato leafroll virus) and Luteovirus (Barley yellow dwarf virus-PAV)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants*
- + 578.944.4 Togaviridae
IN: *Viruses infecting insects and vertebrates*
- + 578.944.41 Alphavirus (genus)
Including: Chikungunya virus, Ross River virus and Sindbis virus
- + 578.944.42 Rubivirus (genus)
Including: Rubella virus
- + 578.944.5 Tombusviridae
Including: Alphanecrovirus (Tobacco necrosis virus A); Betanecrovirus (Tobacco necrosis virus B); Machlomovirus (Maize chlorotic mottle virus); Panicovirus (Panicum mosaic virus); Umbravirus (Tobacco mottle virus); Tombusvirus (Tomato bushy shunt virus); Zeavirus (Maize necrotic streak virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants*
- + 578.944.6 Virgaviridae
Including: Furovirus (Soil-borne wheat mosaic virus); Hordeivirus (Barley stripe mosaic virus); Pomovirus (Potato mop-top virus); Tobravirus (Tobacco rattle virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants*
- + 578.944.61 Tobamovirus (genus)
Including: Tobacco mosaic virus
- + 578.944.7 Potyviridae
Including: Bymovirus (Barley yellow mosaic virus); Poacevirus (Triticum mosaic virus);

- Potyvirus (Potato virus Y); Tritimovirus (Wheat streak mosaic virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants*
- + 578.944.8 Bromoviridae
Including: Alfamovirus (Alfalfa mosaic virus); Bromovirus (Brome mosaic virus); Ilarvirus (Tobacco streak virus); Oleavirus (Olive latent virus 2); Cucumovirus (Cucumber mosaic virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants*
- + 578.945 Unassigned families (II)
- + 578.945.1 Closteroviridae
Including: Closteovirus (Beet yellows virus) and Crinivirus (Lettuce infectious yellow virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants*
- + 578.945.2 Leviviridae
IN: *Viruses infecting Bacteria*
- + 578.945.3 Astroviridae
Including: Avastrovirus (Avian nephritis virus) and Mamastrovirus
IN: *Viruses infecting mammals*
- + 578.945.4 Hepeviridae
Including: Orthohepevirus (Hepatitis E virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates*
- + 578.945.5 Nodaviridae
Including: Betanodavirus (Nervous necrosis virus, NNV)
IN: *Viruses infecting invertebrates and vertebrates*
- + 578.95 Group V ((-)ssRNA viruses)
- + 578.951 Mononegavirales
- + 578.951.1 Bornaviridae
Including: Bornavirus (Bornaviruses)
IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates*
- + 578.951.2 Filoviridae
Including: Cuevavirus (Lloviu virus) and Marbugvirus (Marburg virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates*
- + 578.951.21 Ebolavirus (genus)
Including: Ebola virus
- + 578.951.3 Paramyxoviridae
Including: Avulavirus (Avian paramyxovirus); Henipavirus (Hendra, Nipah and Cedar viruses); Respirovirus (Sendai virus) and Rubulavirus (Mumps virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates*
- + 578.951.31 Morbillivirus (genus)
Including: Measles virus
- + 578.951.4 Rhabdoviridae

- Including: Cytorhabdovirus (Lettuce necrotic yellows virus) and Nucleorhabdovirus (Potato yellow dwarf virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants, invertebrates and vertebrates*
- + 578.951.41 Lyssavirus (genus)
Including: Rabies virus
- + 578.951.5 Nyamiviridae
Including: Nyavirus (Midway virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting invertebrates and vertebrates*
- + 578.952 Unassigned families
Including: Ophioviridae
- + 578.952.1 Arenaviridae
Including: Mammarenavirus (Lymphocytic choriomeningitis virus, Guanarito virus, Junin virus, Lassa virus, Lujo virus, Machupo virus and Sabia virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting mammals*
- + 578.952.2 Bunyaviridae
Including: Orthobunyavirus (Alajuela virus, Batai virus and Tete virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting plants, invertebrates and vertebrates*
- + 578.952.21 Hantavirus (genus)
Including: Hanta virus
- + 578.952.22 Nairovirus (genus)
Including: Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever virus, Ganjam virus and Hazara virus
- + 578.952.3 Orthomyxoviridae
Including: Thogotovirus (Araguari virus and Bourbon virus)
IN: *Viruses infecting invertebrates and vertebrates*
- + 578.952.31 Influenzavirus (genus)
Including: Influenza virus A, B and C
- + 578.96 Group VI (ssRNA-RT viruses)
- + 578.961 Unassigned families
- + 578.961.1 Retroviridae
Including: Alpharetrovirus (Avian leukosis virus and Rous sarcoma virus); Betaretrovirus (Simian retroviruses, SRV); Gammaretrovirus (Feline leukemia virus); Deltaretrovirus (Bovine leukemia virus); Spumavirus (foamy viruses)
IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates*
- + 578.961.11 Lentivirus (genus)
Including: Human immunodeficiency viruses (HIV)
- + 578.97 Group VII (dsDNA-RT viruses)
- + 578.971 Unassigned families
- + 578.971.1 Caulimoviridae

- Including: Solendovirus (Tobacco vein clearing virus); Soymovirus (Soybean chlorotic mottle virus); Caulimovirus (Cauliflower mosaic virus)
 IN: *Viruses infecting plants and invertebrates*
- + 578.971.2 Hepadnaviridae
 IN: *Viruses infecting vertebrates*
- + 578.971.21 Orthohepadnavirus (genus)
 Including: Hepatitis B virus
- + 578.99 Unclassified viruses and virus-like particles
- ! 579.8 **Classification of bacteria**
 SN: *For systematics of bacteria, see 579.9*
- + 579.81/.82 Bacteria according to energy and carbon source
- ! 579.81 **Autotrophic bacteria**
 SN: *Class phototrophic bacteria at 579.812*
 [Revision comment: The scope of this class is broadened: the previous description was "Phototrophic bacteria"]
- x 579.811 (*Rhodospirillales*) → 579.931
 x 579.811.1 (*Rhodospirillaceae*) → 579.931.5
 x 579.811.2/.3 (*Chromatiaceae*) → 579.935.2
 x 579.811.4 (*Chlorobiaceae*) → 579.946.1
- + 579.812 Phototrophic bacteria
- + 579.812.1 Photoheterotrophic bacteria
 Including: Green and purple non-sulphur bacteria and AAPB (aerobic anoxygenic photoheterotrophic bacteria)
- + 579.812.2 Photoautotrophic bacteria
 Including: Oxygenic (cyanobacteria) and anoxygenic photosynthetic bacteria (green and purple sulphur bacteria)
- + 579.813 Chemotrophic bacteria
- + 579.813.1 Chemoheterotrophic bacteria
- + 579.813.2 Chemoautotrophic bacteria
 Including: Chemolithotrophic bacteria
- + 579.813.21 Sulphur bacteria
 Including: Genus *Beggiatoa*
- + 579.813.22 Hydrogen bacteria
 Including: Genus *Hydrogenobacter*
- + 579.813.23 Iron bacteria
 Including: Genera *Thiobacillus* and *Leptospirillum*
- + 579.813.24 Methane bacteria

- + 579.813.25 Nitrifying bacteria
Including: Genera Nitrosomonas and Nitrobacter
- ! 579.82 **Heterotrophic bacteria**
SN: Class gliding bacteria at 579.839.1
- x 579.821 (*Myxobacteriales*) → 579.937
- x 579.821.1 (*Myxococcaceae*) → 579.937.1
- x 579.821.2 (*Archangiaceae*) → 579.937.2
- x 579.821.3 (*Cystobacteriaceae*) → 579.937.3
- x 579.821.4 (*Polyangiaceae*) → 579.937.4
- x 579.822 (*Cytophagales*) → 579.943
- x 579.822.1 (*Cytophagaceae*) → 579.943.1
- x 579.822.2 (*Beggiatoaceae*) → 579.936.5
- x 579.822.3 (*Simonsiellaceae*) → 579.934.8
- x 579.822.4 (*Leucotrichaceae*) → 579.936.5
- x 579.822.9 (*Families and genera of uncertain affiliation*) → 579.943
- + 579.823 Saprophytic bacteria
Including: Genera Zygomonas, Acetobacter and Lactobacillus
- + 579.824 Parasitic bacteria
Including: Genera Salmonella, Mycobacterium and Clostridium
- + 579.825 Symbiotic bacteria
Including: Genera Rhizobium and Azotobacter
- ! 579.83 **Bacteria according to several criteria**
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is changed: the previous description was "Sheathed bacteria"]
- x 579.83 (*Sheathed bacteria...*) → 579.837.1; 579.837.2
- x 579.831 (*Sheathed bacteria*) → 579.837.1
- x 579.832/833 (*Budding and/or appendaged bacteria*) → 579.837.2
- x 579.834 (*Spirochaetes*) → 579.96
- x 579.834.1 (*Spirochaetales*) → 579.961
- x 579.835 (*Spiral and curved bacteria*) → 579.836.3; 579.836.4
- x 579.835.1 (*Spirillaceae*) → 579.933.2
- x 579.835.9 (*Genera of uncertain affiliation*) → 579.836.3; 579.836.4
- + 579.836 Bacteria according to shape
- + 579.836.1 Cocci
- + 579.836.2 Rods
- + 579.836.3 Curved bacteria
- + 579.836.4 Spiral bacteria
- + 579.837 Bacteria according to structure
- + 579.837.1 Sheathed bacteria

- + 579.837.2 Budding and/or appendaged bacteria
Including: Prosthecate and non-prosthecate bacteria and morphologically unusual budding bacteria (involved in iron and manganese deposition)
- + 579.837.3 Non-budding bacteria
- + 579.838 Bacteria according to spore formation
- + 579.838.1 Sporing bacteria
- + 579.838.2 Non-sporing bacteria
- + 579.839 Bacteria according to movement
- + 579.839.1 Gliding bacteria
Including: Single celled gliding bacteria, filamentous gliding bacteria, sulphur-oxidizing gliding bacteria and fruiting gliding bacteria
- + 579.839.2 Flagellated bacteria
- + 579.839.3 Ciliated bacteria
- + 579.84/.86 Bacteria according to Gram staining and shape
- ! 579.84 **Gram negative cocci and rods**
SN: Class Gram negative bacteria in general at 579.93/.96
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is broadened: the previous description was "Gram-negative bacteria"]
- ! 579.841 **Gram negative aerobic and facultative anaerobic cocci**
Including: Genera Neisseria and Moraxella
SN: Class Gram negative aerobic rods at 579.842. Class Legionella at 579.935.5
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is narrowed: the previous description was "Gram-negative aerobic rods and cocci"]
- x 579.841.1 (*Pseudomonadaceae*) → 579.936.2
- x 579.841.2 (*Azotobacteriaceae*) → 579.936.2
- x 579.841.3 (*Rhizobiaceae*) → 579.932.3
- x 579.841.4 (*Methylomonadaceae*) → 579.935/.936
- x 579.841.5 (*Halobacteriaceae*) → 579.991.3
- x 579.841.9 (*Genera of uncertain affiliation*) → 579.841
- ! 579.842 **Gram negative aerobic and facultative anaerobic rods**
Including: Genera Salmonella, Pseudomonas, Vibrio and Haemophilus
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is broadened: the previous description was "Gram-negative facultatively anaerobic rods"]
- x 579.842.1/.2 (*Enterobacteriaceae*) → 579.935.3
- x 579.843 (*Vibrionaceae*) → 579.936.7
- x 579.843.9 (*Genera of uncertain affiliation*) → 579.936.7
- ! 579.844 **Gram negative anaerobic rods**
Including: Genera Bacteroides and Fusobacterium
SN: Class Gram negative anaerobic cocci at 579.845

- [Revision comment: The scope of this class is narrowed: the previous description was "Gram-negative anaerobic bacteria"]
- x 579.844.1 (Bacteroidaceae) → 579.941.1
x 579.844.9 (Genera of uncertain affiliation) → 579.844
- ! 579.845 **Gram negative anaerobic cocci**
Including: Genus Veillonella
- x 579.845.1 (Veillonellaceae) → 579.928.1
x 579.846 (Gram-negative chemolithotrophic bacteria) → 579.813.2
x 579.846.1 (Nitrobacteraceae) → 579.932.4; 579.933.1
x 579.846.2 (Bacteria metabolizing sulphur) → 579.813.21
x 579.846.3 (Siderocapsaceae) → 579.912.1
- ! 579.85 **Miscellaneous (poorly staining species)**
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is changed: the previous description was "Methane-producing bacteria. Endospore-forming rods and cocci"]
- x 579.851 (Methane-producing bacteria) → 579.813.24; 579.991
x 579.852 (Endospore-forming rods and cocci) → 579.838.1
x 579.852.1 (Bacillaceae) → 579.923.1
x 579.852.11 (Bacillus spp) → 579.923.1
x 579.852.13 (Clostridium) → 579.921.2
x 579.852.9 (Genera of uncertain affiliation) → 579.838.1
- ! 579.86 **Gram positive cocci and rods**
SN: Class Gram positive bacteria in general at 579.91/92
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is broadened: the previous description was "Gram-positive cocci. Asporogenous rod-shaped bacteria"]
- x 579.861 (Micrococcaceae) → 579.912.1
x 579.862 (Streptococcaceae) → 579.924.2
x 579.863 (Peptococcaceae) → 579.921.1
x 579.864 (Lactobacillaceae) → 579.924.1
- + 579.865 Gram positive aerobic and facultative anaerobic cocci
Including: Genera Staphylococcus, Streptococcus and Enterococcus
- + 579.866 Gram positive anaerobic cocci
Including: Genus Peptostreptococcus
- + 579.867 Gram positive aerobic and facultative anaerobic rods
Including: Genera Bacillus, Listeria and Corynebacterium
- + 579.868 Gram positive anaerobic rods
Including: Genera Actinomyces and Clostridium
- x 579.869 (Genera of uncertain affiliation) → 579.86
x 579.87 (Actinomycetes and related organisms) → 579.911/913
x 579.871 (Coryneform group of bacteria) → 579.911.4
x 579.872 (Propionibacteriaceae) → 579.912.8
x 579.873 (Actinomycetales) → 579.911/913

- x 579.873.1 (Actinomycetaceae) → 579.911.1
- x 579.873.2 (Mycobacteriaceae) → 579.911.5
- x 579.873.3 (Frankiaceae) → 579.911.8
- x 579.873.4 (Actinoplanaceae) → 579.911/913
- x 579.873.5 (Dermatophilaceae) → 579.912.3
- x 579.873.6 (Nocardiaceae) → 579.911.6
- x 579.873.7 (Streptomycetaceae) → 579.913.1
- x 579.873.8 (Micromonosporaceae) → 579.913.4
- x 579.88 (Rickettsias. Mycoplasmas) → 579.926.1; 579.931.1
- x 579.881 (Rickettsiales) → 579.931
- x 579.881.1 (Rickettsiaceae) → 579.931.1
- x 579.881.2 (Bartonellaceae) → 579.932.1
- x 579.881.3 (Anaplasmataceae) → 579.931.2
- x 579.882 (Chlamydiales) → 579.948
- x 579.887 (Mycoplasmas) → 579.926.1
- x 579.887.1 (Mycoplasmatales) → 579.926
- x 579.887.9 (Genera of uncertain affiliation) → 579.9236.1
- + 579.9 Systematics of bacteria
SN: *Class here bacteria in general*
IN: *Bacteria were also known as Eubacteria*
- + 579.91/92 Gram positive bacteria
SN: *Class here Gram positive bacteria in general. Class Gram positive cocci and rods at 579.86*
- + 579.91 Actinobacteria
Including: Sphaerobacterales
- + 579.911/913 Actinomycetales
Including: Actinoplanaceae
IN: *Actinomycetales were also known as Actinomycetes*
- + 579.911 Actinomycinae. Corynebacterineae. Frankineae
Including: Gordoniaceae, Geodermatophilaceae, Kineosporiaceae and Nakamurellaceae
SN: *This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible*
- + 579.911.1 Actinomycetaceae
Including: Genera Actinomyces and Arcanobacterium
- + 579.911.4 Corynebacteriaceae
Including: Genus Corynebacterium
- + 579.911.5 Mycobacteriaceae
Including: Genus Mycobacterium
- + 579.911.6 Nocardiaceae
Including: Genera Rhodococcus and Nocardia
- + 579.911.8 Frankiaceae
Including: Genus Frankia

- + 579.912 Micrococcineae. Propionibacterineae
Including: Dermacoccaceae, Promicromonosporaceae and Intrasporangiaceae
SN: *This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible*
- + 579.912.1 Micrococcaceae
Including: Genera Micrococcus, Kocuria and Arthrobacter
IN: *Arthrobacter used to belong to deprecated taxon Siderocapsaceae*
- + 579.912.2 Microbacteriaceae
Including: Genera Microbacterium, Agromyces, Leifsonia and Clavibacter
- + 579.912.3 Dermatophilaceae
Including: Genus Dermatophilus
- + 579.912.4 Brevibacteriaceae
Including: Genus Brevibacterium
- + 579.912.5 Cellulomonadaceae
Including: Genus Cellulomonas
- + 579.912.6 Pseudonocardiaceae
Including: Genera Pseudonocardia, Saccharomonospora, Saccharopolyspora and Amycolatopsis
- + 579.912.7 Nocardiodaceae
Including: Genera Nocardioides and Kribbella
- + 579.912.8 Propionibacteriaceae
Including: Genus Propionibacterium
- + 579.913 Streptomycineae. Micromonosporineae. Streptosporangiineae
SN: *This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible*
- + 579.913.1 Streptomycetaceae
Including: Genera Streptomyces and Kitasatospora
- + 579.913.4 Micromonosporaceae
Including: Genera Micromonospora, Catellatospora and Actinoplanes
- + 579.913.7 Streptosporangiaceae
Including: Genera Streptosporangium, Nonomurea and Microbispora
- + 579.913.8 Nocardioisporaceae
Including: Genera Nocardioisporis and Thermobifida
- + 579.913.9 Thermomonosporaceae
Including: Genus Actinomadura
- + 579.915 Bifidobacteriales
- + 579.915.1 Bifidobacteriaceae
Including: Genera Bifidobacterium and Gardnerella

- + 579.916 Acidimicrobiales
- + 579.916.1 Acidimicrobiaceae
Including: Genus Acidimicrobium
- + 579.917 Coriobacteriales
- + 579.917.1 Coriobacteriaceae
Including: Genera Cryptobacterium and Atopobium
- + 579.918 Rubrobacterales
- + 579.918.1 Rubrobacteraceae
Including: Genus Rubrobacter
- + 579.92 Firmicutes
IN: *Firmicutes are also known as Tenericutes*
- + 579.921/922 Clostridia
Including: Thermoanaerobacterales
- + 579.921 Clostridiales
Including: Heliobacteriaceae, Syntrophomonadaceae and Acidaminococcaceae
- + 579.921.1 Peptococcaceae
Including: Genera Peptococcus and Desulfotomaculum
- + 579.921.2 Clostridiaceae
Including: Genus Clostridium
- + 579.921.3 Eubacteriaceae
Including: Genera Eubacterium and Acetobacterium
- + 579.921.4 Lachnospiraceae
Including: Genera Lachnospira and Ruminococcus
- + 579.921.5 Peptostreptococcaceae
Including: Genera Anaerococcus, Peptoniphilus and Peptostreptococcus
- + 579.922 Halanaerobiales
- + 579.922.1 Halanaerobiaceae
Including: Genus Halanaerobium
- + 579.923/924 Bacilli
- + 579.923 Bacillales
- + 579.923.1 Bacillaceae
Including: Genera Bacillus, Virgibacillus, Geobacillus, Halobacillus, Exiguobacterium and Anoxybacillus
- + 579.923.2 Listeriaceae
Including: Genus Listeria

- + 579.923.3 Staphylococcaceae
Including: Genera Staphylococcus and Macrococcus
- + 579.923.4 Alicyclobacillaceae
Including: Genus Alicyclobacillus
- + 579.923.5 Paenibacillaceae
Including: Genera Paenibacillus and Brevibacillus
- + 579.923.6 Planococcaceae
Including: Genera Planococcus, Planomicrobium and Sporosarcina
- + 579.924 Lactobacillales
- + 579.924.1 Lactobacillaceae
Including: Genera Lactobacillus and Pediococcus
- + 579.924.2 Streptococcaceae
Including: Genera Streptococcus and Lactococcus
- + 579.924.3 Enterococcaceae
Including: Genus Enterococcus
- + 579.924.4 Leuconostocaceae
Including: Genera Leuconostoc and Weissella
- + 579.924.5 Carnobacteriaceae
Including: Genera Carnobacterium and Trichococcus
- + 579.926/927 Mollicutes
- + 579.926 Mycoplasmatales. Haloplasmatales. Acholeplasmatales
SN: This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible
- + 579.926.1 Mycoplasmataceae
Including: Genera Mycoplasma and Ureaplasma
- + 579.926.4 Haloplasmataceae
- + 579.926.7 Acholeplasmataceae
Including: Genera Acholeplasma and Phytoplasma
- + 579.927 Entomoplasmatales. Anaeroplasmatales
SN: This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible
- + 579.927.1 Spiroplasmataceae
Including: Genus Spiroplasma
- + 579.927.2 Entomoplasmataceae
Including: Genera Entomoplasma and Mesoplasma
- + 579.927.5 Anaeroplasmataceae
Including: Genus Anaeroplasma

- + 579.928 Negativicutes. Selenomonadales
- + 579.928.1 Veillonellaceae
Including: Genera Veillonella and Selenomonas
- + 579.93/96 Gram negative bacteria
SN: *Class here Gram negative bacteria in general. Class Gram negative cocci and rods at 579.84*
- + 579.93 Proteobacteria
- + 579.931/932 Alphaproteobacteria
Including: Magnetococcales, Pelagibacterales, Holosporales and Parvularculales
- + 579.931 Rickettsiales. Rhodospirillales. Rhodobacterales
SN: *This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible*
- + 579.931.1 Rickettsiaceae
Including: Genus Rickettsia
- + 579.931.2 Anaplasmataceae
Including: Genera Anaplasma, Neorickettsia, Wolbachia and Ehrlichia
- + 579.931.3 Acetobacteraceae
Including: Genera Acetobacter and Gluconacetobacter
- + 579.931.5 Rhodospirillaceae
Including: Genera Rhodospirillum and Azospirillum
- + 579.931.7 Rhodobacteraceae
Including: Genera Rhodobacter, Maricaulis, Paracoccus, Rhodovulum and Hyphomonas
- + 579.932 Rhizobiales. Sphingomonadales. Caulobacterales
Including: Hyphomicrobiaceae, Rhodobiaceae and Methylobacteriaceae
SN: *This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible*
- + 579.932.1 Bartonellaceae
Including: Genus Bartonella
- + 579.932.2 Brucellaceae
Including: Genera Brucella and Ochrobactrum
- + 579.932.3 Rhizobiaceae
Including: Genera Rhizobium, Ensifer and Agrobacterium
- + 579.932.4 Bradyrhizobiaceae
Including: Genera Bradyrhizobium and Nitrobacter
IN: *Nitrobacter used to belong to deprecated taxon Nitrobacteraceae*
- + 579.932.5 Phyllobacteriaceae
Including: Genera Aminobacter, Mesorhizobium and Phyllobacterium
- + 579.932.6 Sphingomonadaceae

- Including: Genera *Sphingomonas*, *Sphingobium*, *Novosphingobium* and *Erythrobacter*
- + 579.932.8 Caulobacteraceae
Including: Genera *Caulobacter* and *Brevundimonas*
- + 579.933/934 Betaproteobacteria
Including: Hydrogenophilales, Methylophilales and Rhodocyclales
- + 579.933 Nitrosomonadales
- + 579.933.1 Nitrosomonadaceae
Including: Genera *Nitrosomonas* and *Nitrosospira*
IN: *Nitrosomonas* used to belong to deprecated taxon *Nitrobacteraceae*
- + 579.933.2 Spirillaceae
Including: Genus *Spirillum*
- + 579.934 Burkholderiales. Neisseriales
SN: *This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible*
- + 579.934.1 Alcaligenaceae
Including: Genera *Alcaligenes*, *Achromobacter* and *Bordetella*
- + 579.934.2 Burkholderiaceae
Including: Genera *Burkholderia* and *Cupriavidus*
- + 579.934.3 Comamonadaceae
Including: Genera *Sphaerotilus* and *Leptothrix*
- + 579.934.4 Oxalobacteraceae
Including: Genera *Oxalobacter* and *Herbaspirillum*
- + 579.934.5 Comamonadaceae
Including: Genera *Comamonas* and *Acidovorax*
- + 579.934.8 Neisseriaceae
Including: Genera *Neisseria* and *Aquaspirillum*
SN: *Class here species included in deprecated taxon Simonsiellaceae*
- + 579.935/936 Gammaproteobacteria
Including: Acidithiobacillales, Alteromonadales, Cardiobacteriales and Methylococcales
SN: *Class here species included in deprecated taxon Methylomonadaceae*
- + 579.935 Aeromonadales. Chromatiales. Enterobacteriales. Legionellales. Oceanospirillales
Including: Ectothiorhodospiraceae and Halothiobacillaceae
SN: *This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible*
- + 579.935.1 Aeromonadaceae
Including: Genus *Aeromonas*
- + 579.935.2 Chromatiaceae
Including: Genera *Chromatium* and *Thiocapsa*

- + 579.935.3 Enterobacteriaceae
Including: Genera Salmonella, Brenneria, Pectobacterium, Escherichia, Yersinia, Proteus, Enterobacter, Klebsiella, Serratia and Citrobacter
- + 579.935.5 Legionellaceae
Including: Genus Legionella
- + 579.935.6 Coxiellaceae
Including: Genera Coxiella and Rickettsiella
- + 579.935.8 Halomonadaceae
Including: Genera Halomonas and Chromohalobacter
- + 579.935.9 Oceanospirillaceae
Including: Genera Oceanospirillum and Marinomonas
- + 579.936 Pasteurellales. Pseudomonadales. Thiotrichales. Vibrionales. Xanthomonadales
SN: *This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible*
- + 579.936.1 Pasteurellaceae
Including: Genera Pasteurella, Actinobacillus and Haemophilus
- + 579.936.2 Pseudomonadaceae
Including: Genera Rhizobacter, Azotobacter and Pseudomonas
SN: *Class here species belonging to deprecated taxon Azotobacteriaceae*
- + 579.936.3 Moraxellaceae
Including: Genera Moraxella, Psychrobacter and Acinetobacter
- + 579.936.4 Francisellaceae
Including: Genus Francisella
- + 579.936.5 Thiotrichaceae
Including: Genera Beggiatoa, Thiothrix and Leucothrix
SN: *Class here species included in deprecated taxa Beggiatoaceae and Leucotrichaceae*
- + 579.936.7 Vibrionaceae
Including: Genera Vibrio and Photobacterium
- + 579.936.8 Xanthomonadaceae
Including: Genera Xanthomonas, Stenotrophomonas and Lysobacter
- + 579.937/938 Deltaproteobacteria
Including: Desulfobacterales, Desulfarculales, Desulfovibrionales, Desulfurellales and Syntrophobacterales
- + 579.937 Myxococcales
IN: *Myxococcales were also known as Myxobacterales*
- + 579.937.1 Myxococcaceae
Including: Genus Myxococcus
- + 579.937.2 Archangiaceae

- Including: Genus Archangium
- + 579.937.3 Cystobacteraceae
Including: Genus Cystobacter
- + 579.937.4 Polyangiaceae
Including: Genera Polyangium, Chondromyces and Sorangium
- + 579.938 Desulfuromonadales. Bdellovibrionales
SN: This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible
- + 579.938.1 Geobacteraceae
Including: Genus Geobacter
- + 579.938.2 Desulfuromonadaceae
Including: Genus Desulfuromonas
- + 579.938.4 Bdellovibrionaceae
Including: Genus Bdellovibrio
- + 579.939 Epsilonproteobacteria
- + 579.939.1 Helicobacteraceae
Including: Genera Helicobacter and Sulfurimonas
- + 579.939.2 Campylobacteraceae
Including: Genus Campylobacter
- + 579.94 FCB group. PVC group
SN: This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible
- + 579.941/946 FCB group (Bacteroidetes-Fibrobacteres-Chlorobi)
- + 579.941/944 Bacteroidetes
- + 579.941 Bacteroidales
- + 579.941.1 Bacteroidaceae
Including: Genus Bacteroides
- + 579.941.2 Porphyromonadaceae
Including: Genus Porphyromonas
- + 579.941.3 Prevotellaceae
Including: Genus Prevotella
- + 579.942 Flavobacteriales
- + 579.942.1 Flavobacteriaceae
Including: Genera Flavobacterium, Chryseobacterium, Gillisia, Tenacibaculum and Bizionia
- + 579.942.2 Cryomorphaceae
Including: Genus Algoriphagus

- + 579.943 Cytophagales
- + 579.943.1 Cytophagaceae
Including: Genus Cytophaga
- + 579.944 Sphingobacteriales
Including: Saprospiraceae and Flammeovirgaceae
- + 579.944.1 Sphingobacteriaceae
Including: Genera Sphingobacterium and Pedobacter
- + 579.944.2 Flexibacteraceae
Including: Genus Flexibacter
- + 579.944.3 Crenotrichaceae
Including: Genus Chitinophaga
- + 579.945 Fibrobacteres. Fibrobacterales
- + 579.945.1 Fibrobacteraceae
Including: Genus Fibrobacter
- + 579.946 Chlorobi. Chlorobiales
- + 579.946.1 Chlorobiaceae
Including: Genera Chlorobium and Chlorobaculum
- + 579.947/949 PVC group (Planctomycetes-Verrucomicrobia-Chlamydiae)
- + 579.947 Planctomycetes. Planctomycetales
- + 579.947.1 Planctomycetaceae
Including: Genera Planctomyces and Gemmata
- + 579.948 Chlamydiae. Chlamydiales
Including: Parachlamydiaceae, Simkaniaceae and Waddliaceae
- + 579.948.1 Chlamydiaceae
Including: Genera Chlamydia and Chlamydothrix
- + 579.949 Verrucomicrobia. Verrucomicrobiales
- + 579.949.1 Verrucomicrobiaceae
Including: Genus Verrucomicrobium
- + 579.95 Fusobacteria. Gemmatimonadetes. Nitrospira. Aquificae. Deinococcus-Thermus
SN: This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible
- + 579.951 Fusobacteria. Fusobacteriales
- + 579.951.1 Leptotrichiaceae
Including: Genus Leptotrichia
- + 579.951.2 Fusobacteriaceae

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- Including: Genera *Fusobacterium* and *Streptobacillus*
 - + 579.952 Gemmatimonadetes. Gemmatimonadales
 - + 579.952.1 Gemmatimonadaceae
Including: Genus *Gemmatimonas*
 - + 579.953 Nitrospira. Nitrospirales
 - + 579.953.1 Nitrospiraceae
Including: Genera *Nitrospira* and *Leptospirillum*
 - + 579.954 Aquificae. Aquificales
 - + 579.954.1 Aquificaceae
Including: Genera *Aquifex*, *Hydrogenobacter* and *Persephonella*
 - + 579.955/956 Deinococcus-Thermus
 - + 579.955 Deinococcales
 - + 579.955.1 Deinococcaceae
Including: Genus *Deinococcus*
 - + 579.956 Thermales
 - + 579.956.1 Thermaceae
Including: Genera *Thermus* and *Meiothermus*
 - + 579.96 Spirochaetes
 - + 579.961 Spirochaetales
 - + 579.961.1 Spirochaetaceae
Including: Genera *Borrelia*, *Spirochaeta* and *Treponema*
 - + 579.961.2 Leptospiraceae
Including: Genus *Leptospira*
 - + 579.961.3 Brevinemataceae
Including: Genus *Brevinema*
 - + 579.961.4 Brachyspiraceae
Including: Genus *Brachyspira*
 - + 579.97 Cyanobacteria
IN: *Cyanobacteria* were also known as *Cyanophyta* and *blue-green algae*
 - + 579.971 Chroococcales
Including: Aphanothecaceae, Cyanothrichaceae, Entophysalidaceae, Gomphosphaeriaceae and Stichosiphonaceae
IN: *Chroococcales* is also known as *Cyanobacteria* (!)
 - + 579.971.1 Chroococcaceae
Including: Genus *Chroococcus*

- + 579.971.2 Cyanobacteriaceae
Including: Genus Cyanobacterium
- + 579.971.3 Microcystaceae
Including: Genus Microcystis
- + 579.972 Pleurocapsales
Including: Hydrococcaceae
IN: *Pleurocapsales is also known as Cyanobacteria (II)*
- + 579.972.1 Dermocarpellaceae
Including: Genera Dermocarpella, Cyanocystis and Stanieria
- + 579.972.2 Pleurocapsaceae
Genera Myxosarcina, Chroococciopsis and Pleurocapsa
- + 579.972.3 Xenococcaceae
Including: Genus Xenococcus
- + 579.973 Oscillatoriales
Including: Coleofasciculaceae, Cyanothecaceae, Gomontiellaceae and Homoeotrichaceae
IN: *Oscillatoriales is also known as Cyanobacteria (III)*
- + 579.973.1 Borziaceae
Including: Genus Borzia
- + 579.973.2 Microcoleaceae
Including: Genera Arthrospira and Microcoleus
- + 579.973.3 Oscillatoriaceae
Including: Genus Oscillatoria
- + 579.973.4 Spirulaceae
Including: Genus Spirulina
- + 579.974 Nostocales
Including: Capsosiraceae, Chlorogloeopsidaceae, Fortieaceae, Godleyaceae, Hapalosiphonaceae, Scytonemataceae, Stigonemataceae, Symphyonemataceae and Tolypothrichaceae
IN: *Nostocales is also known as Cyanobacteria (IV)*
- + 579.974.1 Aphanizomenonaceae
Including: Genera Anabaenopsis, Cyanospira and Nodularia
- + 579.974.2 Gloeotrichiaceae
Including: Genus Calothrix
- + 579.974.3 Nostocaceae
Including: Genera Anabaena, Nostoc and Cylindrospermum
- + 579.974.4 Rivulariaceae
Including: Genus Rivularia
- + 579.975 Stigonematales

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- IN: *Stigonematales* is also known as *Cyanobacteria* (V)
- + 579.975.1 Stigonemataceae
Including: Genus *Stigonema*
 - + 579.98 Acidobacteria. Chloroflexi. Chrysiogenetes. Deferribacteres. Dictyoglomi.
Thermodesulfobacteria. Thermotogae. Thermomicrobia
SN: *This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible*
 - + 579.981 Acidobacteria. Acidobacteriales
 - + 579.981.1 Acidobacteriaceae
Including: Genera *Acidobacterium* and *Geothrix*
 - + 579.982 Chloroflexi
 - + 579.982.1 Chloroflexaceae
Including: Genus *Chloroflexus*
 - + 579.982.2 Herpetosiphonaceae
Including: Genus *Herpetosiphon*
 - + 579.982.3 Anaerolineaceae
Including: Genus *Anaerolinea*
 - + 579.983 Chrysiogenetes. Chrysiogenales
 - + 579.983.1 Chrysiogenaceae
Including: Genus *Chrysiogenes*
 - + 579.984 Deferribacteres. Deferribacterales
 - + 579.984.1 Deferribacteraceae
Including: Genera *Deferribacter* and *Geovibrio*
 - + 579.985 Dictyoglomi. Dictyoglomales
 - + 579.985.1 Dictyoglomaceae
Including: Genus *Dictyoglomus*
 - + 579.986 Thermodesulfobacteria. Thermodesulfobacteriales
 - + 579.986.1 Thermodesulfobacteriaceae
Including: Genera *Thermodesulfobacterium* and *Thermodesulfatator*
 - + 579.987 Thermotogae. Thermotogales
 - + 579.987.1 Thermotogaceae
Including: Genera *Thermotoga* and *Petrotoga*
 - + 579.988 Thermomicrobia
 - + 579.988.1 Thermomicrobiaceae
Including: Genus *Thermomicrobium*

- + 579.99 Archaea
IN: *Archaea were also known as Archaeobacteria*
- + 579.991 Euryarchaeota
SN: *Class here methane-producing bacteria (methanogenes) in general*
- + 579.991.1 Thermoplasmata. Thermoplasmatales. Thermoplasmataceae
Including: Genus Thermoplasma
- + 579.991.2 Methanobacteria. Methanobacteriales. Methanobacteriaceae
Including: Genera Methanobacterium and Methanobrevibacter
- + 579.991.3 Halobacteria. Halobacteriales. Halobacteriaceae
Including: Genera Halobacterium, Haloferax, Halorubrum, Natrionalba and Haloarcula
- + 579.991.4 Methanococci. Methanococcales. Methanococcaceae
Including: Genera Methanococcus and Methanocaldococcus
- + 579.991.5 Thermococci. Thermococcales. Thermococcaceae
Including: Genus Thermococcus
- + 579.991.6 Archaeoglobi. Archaeoglobales. Archaeoglobaceae
Including: Genus Archaeoglobus
- + 579.991.7 Methanopyri. Methanopyrales. Methanopyraceae
Including: Genus Methanopyrus
- + 579.991.8/9 Methanomicrobia
- + 579.991.8 Methanomicrobiales. Methanomicrobiaceae
Including: Genera Methanomicrobium and Methanoculleus
- + 579.991.9 Methanosarcinales. Methanosarcinaceae
Including: Genera Methanosarcina and Methanolobus
- + 579.992 Nanoarchaeota
- + 579.992.1 Nanoarchaceae
Including: Genus Nanoarchaeum
- + 579.993 Crenarchaeota. Thermoprotei
IN: *Crenarchaeota were also known as Eocyta*
- + 579.993.1 Sulfolobales. Sulfolobaceae
Including: Genus Sulfolobus
- + 579.993.3 Thermoproteales. Thermoproteaceae
Including: Genera Thermoproteus and Pyrobaculum
- + 579.993.5 Caldisphaerales. Caldisphaeraceae
Including: Genus Caldisphaera
- + 579.993.7/8 Desulfurococcales
- + 579.993.7 Desulfurococcaceae

- Including: Genera *Desulfurococcus* and *Staphylothermus*
- + 579.993.8 Pyrodictiaceae
Including: Genus *Pyrodictium*
- x 582.23 (*Bacteria*) → 579.9
- x 582.231 (*Schizomycota (Bacteriophyta). Bacteria (as plants)*) → 579.9
- x 582.232 (*Cyanophyta (Cyanophyceae...)*) → 579.97
- x 582.233 (*Archaea...*) → 579.99; 579.991.1; 579.991.2; 579.991.3; 579.993.1
- x 582.24 (*Protista (Protoctista). Chromista. Protozoa*) → 582.25; 593.1
- x 582.241 (*Myxomycota (Mycetozoa...)*) → 593.122.1
- x 582.243 (*Hyphochytriomycota*) → 582.256.7
- x 582.244 (*Oomycota (Oomycetes)*) → 582.256.8
- x 582.244.1 (*Saprolegniales*) → 582.256.81
- x 582.244.2 (*Peronosporales*) → 582.256.82
- x 582.245 (*Plasmodiophoromycota*) → 593.141
- x 582.245.1 (*Plasmodiophorales*) → 593.141
- + 582.25 Chromista
IN: *Chromista* were also known as *Chromophyta*, *Chromobiota* and *Chromobionta*
- + 582.255 Bacillariophyta (diatoms)
- + 582.255.1 Coscinodiscophyceae
Including: Asterolamprales (*Asterolampraceae*, genus *Asteromphalus*); Melosirales (*Melosiraceae*, genus *Melosira* and *Hyalodiscaceae*, genus *Hyalodiscus*); Rhizosoleniales (*Rhizosoleniaceae*, genus *Rhizosolenia*); Stephanopyxales (*Stephanopyxidaceae*, genus *Stephanopyxis*); Triceratiales (*Triceratiaceae*, genus *Triceratium*)
IN: *Coscinodiscophyceae* were also known as *Centrales*
- + 582.255.11 Coscinodiscales
Including: *Coscinodiscaceae* (genus *Coscinodiscus*); *Heliopeltaceae* (genus *Actinoptychus*); *Hemidiscaceae* (genera *Actinocyclus*, *Hemidiscus* and *Azpeitia*)
- + 582.255.2 Bacillariophyceae
Including: Cocconeidales (*Cocconeidaceae*, genus *Cocconeis* and *Achnanthidiaceae*, genera *Achnanthidium* and *Planothidium*); Cymbellales (*Gomphonemataceae*, genera *Gomphonema* and *Encyonema*, and *Cymbellaceae*, genus *Cymbella*); Eunotiales (*Eunotiaceae*, genera *Eunotia* and *Actinella*); Fragiliales (*Fragilariaceae*, genera *Fragilaria* and *Synedra*); Lyrellales (*Lyrellaceae*, genus *Lyrella*); Rhabdonematales (*Rhabdonemataceae*, genus *Rhabdonema*); Surirellales (*Surirellaceae*, genus *Surirella*); Tabellariales (*Tabellariaceae*, genera *Asterionella*, *Meridion* and *Tabellaria*); Thalassiophysales (*Catenulaceae*, genus *Amphora*)
- + 582.255.21 Bacillariales
Including: *Bacillariaceae* (genera *Bacillaria*, *Nitzschia*, *Fragilariopsis*, *Denticula* and *Cylindrotheca*)
- + 582.255.22 Naviculales
Including: *Naviculaceae* (genera *Navicula* and *Gyrosigma*) and *Diploneidaceae* (genus *Diploneis*)
- + 582.255.3 Mediophyceae
Including: Eupodiscales (*Eupodiscaeae*, genera *Odontella* and *Auliscus*); Chaetocerotales (*Chaetoceraceae*, genus *Chaetoceros*); Stephanodiscales (*Stephanodiscaceae*, genera *Cyclotella*

- and Stephanodiscus); Thalassionematales (Thalassionemataceae, genus Thalassionema); Thalassiosirales (Thalassiosiraceae, genus Thalassiosira, and Skeletonemataceae, genus Skeletonema)
- + 582.256 Heterokonta / Stramenopiles
- + 582.256.1 Bolidophyceae (bolidophytes)
Including: Parmales (triparmaceae, genus Triparma)
- + 582.256.2 Chrysophyceae (golden algae)
Including: Chromulinales (Chromulinaceae, genera Chromulina and Ochromonas, and Dinobryaceae, genera Chrysococcus, Epipyxis and Dinobryon); Eustigmatales (Eustigmataceae, genus Eustigmatos); Hibberdiales (Stylococcaceae, genus Chrysopyxis); Prymnesiales (Prymnesiaceae, genus Prymnesium)
IN: *Chrysophyceae* were also known as *Chrysophyta* or *chrysomonads*. *Chromulinales* were also known as *Chromomonadina*
- + 582.256.3 Phaeophyceae (brown algae)
Including: Desmarestiales (Desmarestiaceae, genus Desmarestia); Dictyotales (Dictyotaceae, genus Dictyota); Sphacelariales (Sphacelariaceae, genus Sphacelaria)
IN: *Phaeophyceae* were also known as *Phaeophyta*
- + 582.256.31 Fucales
Including: Durvillaeaceae (the Cochayuyo, genus Durvillaea) and Himanthaliaceae (the Thongweed, genus Himanthalia)
- + 582.256.311 Fucaceae
Including: Wracks (genera Fucus, Pelvetia and Ascophyllum)
- + 582.256.312 Sargassaceae
Including: The Hijiki, the Japanese Wireweed and the Sargassum (genus Sargassum) and genera Cystoseira and Turbinaria
- + 582.256.32 Laminariales
Including: Agaraceae (genus Agarum); Alariaceae (the Dabberlock, genus Alaria and the Wakame, genus Undaria); Lessoniaceae (the Arame, genus Eisenia)
- + 582.256.321 Laminariaceae
Including: Kelps and the Oarweed (genus Laminaria); the Giant Kelp (genus Macrocystis); the Kombu and the Sugar Kelp (genus Saccharina)
- + 582.256.33 Ectocarpales
Including: Chordariaceae (the Mozuku, genus Cladosiphon, and genera Streblonema and Punctaria) and Ectocarpaceae (genus Ectocarpus)
- + 582.256.4 Raphidophyceae
Including: Chattonellales (Chattonellaceae, genera Chattonella and Heterosigma, and Vacuolariaceae, genera Goniostonum and Vacuolaria)
IN: *Raphidophyceae* were also known as *Raphidophyte*, *Chloromonadophyceae* and *Chloromonadineae*
- + 582.256.5 Synurophyceae (synurids)
Including: Synurales (Mallomonadaceae, genus Mallomonas and Synuraceae, genus Synura)
- + 582.256.6 Xanthophyceae (yellow-green algae)

- Including: Botrydiales (Botrydiaceae, genus Botrydium); Mischococcales (Pleurochloridaceae, genus Pleurochloris); Tribonematales (Heteropediaceae, genus Heterococcus and Tribonemataceae, genus Tribonema); Vaucheriales (Vaucheriaceae, genus Vaucheria)
IN: *Xanthophyceae* were also known as *Xanthophyta*
- + 582.256.7 Hyphochytriomycetes
IN: *Hyphochytriomycetes* were also known as *Hyphochytriomycota*
- + 582.256.8 Oomycetes (water moulds)
IN: *Oomycetes* were also known as *Oomycota*
- + 582.256.81 Saprolegniales
- + 582.256.82 Peronosporales
- + 582.257 Cryptophyta. Haptophyta
SN: *This class is provided for the convenience of grouping, when more specific classification is not required or is not possible*
- + 582.257.1 Cryptophyta
Including: Cryptomonadales (Cryptomonadaceae, genus Cryptomonas) and Pyrenomonadales (Chroomonadaceae, genus Chroomonas and Pyrenomonadaceae, genus Rhodomonas)
IN: *Cryptophyta* used to be known as *cryptomonads*
- + 582.257.2 Haptophyta
Including: Coccolithales (Coccolithaceae, genus Coccolithus and Calyptosphaeraceae, genus Calyptosphaera) and Prymnesiales (Prymnesiaceae, genera Chrysochromulina and Prymnesium)
IN: *Haptophyta* used to be known as *Prymnesiophyta*
- x 582.261 (*Chrysophyta*) → 582.256.2
- x 582.261.1 (*Bacillariophyceae. Diatoms*) → 582.255; 582.255.2
- x 582.261.2 (*Chrysophyceae: Golden-brown algae*) → 582.256.2
- x 582.268 (*Xanthophyta: Yellow-green algae*) → 582.256.6
- ! 582.27 Algae
Including: Seaweeds, pond scum, phytoplankton
SN: *Class here algae in general. Class Rhodophyta, Glaucophyta, Chlorophyta and Charophyta at 582.31 and its subdivisions. Class Chrysophyceae, Phaeophyceae and Xanthophyceae at 582.252 and its subdivisions. Class here also phycology. Alternatively denote phycology as a branch of study by colon combination with 001*
IN: *Algae is a traditional, informal group (folk division), encompassing taxa and species belonging to different kingdoms. It has been preserved in UDC for the convenience of indexing*
- x 582.272 (*Phaeophyta...*) → 582.256.3; 582.256.301; 582.256.321
- x 582.276 (*Pyrrophyta. Dinoflagellates. Cryptophytes...*) → 582.257.1; 593.18
- x 582.277 (*Euglenophyta: Euglenoids*) → 593.161
- ! 593.1 **Protista**
SN: *Class here Protozoa in general. Class here Heliozoa and Myxosporidia*
IN: *Protista are also known as Protoctista and Protozoa*
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is broadened: the previous description was "Protozoa"]

- ! 593.11 **Basic Opisthokonta**
Including: Rozellida, Fonticulida, Nucleariida, Mesomycetozoea, Filasterea and Choanoflagellata
SN: *Class Rhizopoda at 593.12*
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is broadened: the previous description was "Rhizopoda in general"]
- ! 593.12 Amoebozoa
SN: *Class Foraminifera at 593.142*
IN: *Amoebae were also known as Rhizopoda*
- ! 593.121 **Lobosa**
SN: *Class Amoebae at 593.121.2*
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is broadened: the previous description was "Amoebae"]
- + 593.121.1 Discosea
- + 593.121.2 Tubulinea
Including: Amoebidae (genera Amoeba and Chaos); Hartmannellidae (limax amoebae, genus Hartmannella); Arcellinidae (lobose testate amoebae, genus Arcella)
- + 593.122 Conosa
- + 593.122.1 Mycetozoa
Including: Protostelia, Myxogastria and Dictyostelia
IN: *Mycetozoa were also known as Myxomycota*
- + 593.122.2 Archamoebae
Including: Genera Entamoeba and Endolimax
- x 593.13 (*Heliozoa*) → 593.1
- ! 593.14 **Rhizaria**
SN: *Class Radiolaria at 593.143*
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is broadened: the previous description was "Radiolaria. Marine plankton"]
- + 593.141 Cercozoa
Including: Chlorarachniophyta, Phytomyxea (Plasmodiophoromycota and Phagomyxida), Proteomyxidea, Sarcomonadea / Monadoflora, Imbricatea / Silicoflora and Phaeodarea
- + 593.142 Foraminifera
Including: Globigerinida, Lagenida, Miliolida, Rotaliida and Textulariida, as well as strictly extinct Fusulinida and Involutinida
- + 593.143 Radiolaria
Including: Spasmaria (Acantharea and Taxopodida) and Polycistina (Nassellaria and Spumellaria)
IN: *Radiolaria are also known as Radiozoa*
- ! 593.16 **Excavata**
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is broadened: the previous description was "Flagellata / Mastigophora"]

- ! 593.161 **Euglenozoa**
SN: *Class Trypanosomatidae at 593.161.1*
IN: *Euglenozoa were also known as Euglenophyta*
[Revision comment: The scope of this class is broadened: the previous description was "Euflagellata. Trypanosomatidae"]
- + 593.161.1 Kinetoplastida
Including: Trypanosomatidae (genus Trypanosoma)
- + 593.161.2 Diplonemea
Including: Diplonemidae (genus Diplonema)
- ! 593.161.3 **Euglenida**
IN: *Euglenida are also known as Euglenophyceae*
Including: Euglenaceae (genus Euglena)
- x 593.161.4 (*Chromomonadina*) → 582.256.2
x 593.161.52 (*Volvocidae*) → 582.303.2
x 593.162 (*Dinoflagellata. Peridiniidae*) → 593.18; 593.181
x 593.163 (*Cystoflagellata. Noctiluca*) → 593.182
- + 593.164 Percolozoa
IN: *Percolozoa are also known as Heterolobosea*
Including: Schizopyrenida and Acrasida
- + 593.165 Metamonada
Including: Retortamonadida, Diplomonadida, Parabasalia and Oxymonadida
- + 593.17/19 Alveolata
- ! 593.17 **Ciliophora (ciliates)**
IN: *Ciliophora are also known as Ciliata or Infusoria*
- ! 593.171 **Peniculida (peniculids)**
Including: *Parameciidae (genera Paramecium and Frontonia)*
- ! 593.172 **Heterotrichea**
Including: *Stentoridae (trumpet animalcules, genus Stentor) and Spirostomidae (genus Spirostomum)*
- ! 593.173 **Oligotrichia**
- ! 593.174 **Hypotrichia**
- ! 593.175 **Peritrichia**
Including: *Trichodinidae (genus Trichodina)*
- 593.176 Suctoria
- + 593.18 Dinoflagellata (dinoflagellates)
IN: *Dinoflagellata were also known as Pyrrophyta, Dinophyta and Dinophyceae*
- + 593.181 Dinophyceae
Including: Peridinales (Glenodiniaceae, genus Glenodinium; Protoperidiniaceae,

- genus *Protoperidinium*; Thoracosphaeraceae, genus *Thoracosphaera*); Gymnodiniales (Gymnodiniaceae, genera *Gymnodinium* and *Gyrodinium*; Polykrikaceae, genus *Polykrikos*; Warnowiaceae); Gonyaulacales (Ceratiaceae, genera *Tripos* and *Ceratium*, and Gonyaulacaceae, genus *Gonyaulax*); Dinophysiales (Dinophysaceae, genus *Dinophysis*)
- + 593.182 **Noctiluca**
 Including: Noctiluciales (Noctilucaceae, genus *Noctiluca* and Leptodiscaceae, genus *Leptodinium*)
 IN: *Noctiluca* were also known as *Noctiluciphyceae* and used to be included in taxon *Cystoflagellata*
- + 593.183 **Syndinea**
 Including: Coccidinales / Syndiniales (Syndiniaceae, genera *Syndinium* and *Hematodinium*, and Coccidiniaceae, genus *Coccidinium*)
 IN: *Syndinea* were also known as *Syndiniophyceae*
- ! 593.19 **Apicomplexa**
 IN: *Apicomplexa* were also known as *Sporozoa*
- ! 593.191 **Gregarina**
 IN: *Gregarina* are also known as *Gregarinasina*
- ! 593.192 **Coccidia**
 IN: *Coccidia* are also known as *Coccidiasina*
- + 593.192.1 **Sarcocystidae**
 Including: Genera *Toxoplasma*, *Isospora* and *Sarcocystis*
 IN: *Sarcocystidae* were also known as *Sarcosporidia*
- + 593.192.2 **Eimeriidae**
 Including: Genus *Cyclospora*
- + 593.192.3 **Cryptosporidiidae**
 Including: *Cryptosporidium*
- x 593.193 (*Sarcosporidia*) → 593.192.1
- x 593.194 (*Myxosporidia*) → 593.1
- x 593.195 (*Microsporidia*) → 582.289
- + 593.196 **Aconoidasida**
 IN: *Aconoidasida* were among the groups known as *Hematozoa*
- + 593.196.1 **Plasmodiidae**
 Including: Genus *Plasmodium*
- + 593.196.2 **Babesiidae**
 Including: Genus *Babesia*